

Technical Note on Quality Assessment for GRUS-1

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1. INTRODUCTION

This technical note details the results of the preliminary data quality assessments (geometric calibration, radiometric calibration and image quality) performed on a sample of georectified bundle products generated from the optical Earth Observation (EO) GRUS-1 mission.

The aforementioned data quality assessments are performed in accordance with the assessment guidelines, detailed in [RD-1, RD-2], that constitute the European Space Agency (ESA) Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot (EDAP) Project's *EO Mission Data Quality Assessment Framework*. An important representation of the latter framework, constructed by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL), is what is known as the *maturity matrix*. It is a diagrammatic summary of the following:

- **Documentation Review:** the EDAP optical team reviews materials provided by the data provider and / or operator (e.g. ancillary / auxiliary data and documentation), some of which may not be publicly available, or even the scientific community (e.g. published papers). The results are detailed in Section 3 (covering the first four columns of the maturity matrix, see Table 3-1).
- **Data Quality Assessments:** the EDAP optical team performs data quality assessments (i.e. validation assessments), independently of those performed by the data provider and / or operator. The results are detailed in Section 4 (covering the last column of the maturity matrix, see Table 3-1).

The above data quality assessments are performed by the project's optical team using the appropriate in-house and open-source ad-hoc scripts / tools.

It is important to note the purpose of the *EDAP EO Mission Data Quality Assessment Framework* is to ensure that the delivered commercial mission data is fit for purpose and that all decisions regarding the inclusion of the commercial mission as an ESA third party mission can be made fairly and with confidence.

1.1 Reference Documents

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. EDAP.REP.001 Generic EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, 1.1 23 May 2019
- RD-2. EDAP.REP.002 Optical Mission Quality Assessment Guidelines, v1.0, 16 October 2019.
- RD-3. Axelspace - AxelGlobe Image Specification sheet, 13 December 2021
- RD-4. Axelspace - GRUS-1 User Handbook. Draft. Not public.
- RD-5. Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., et al. 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3, 160018. (doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18)

- RD-6. SPOT Image Quality Performances, CNES C443-NT-0-296-CN, https://www.intelligence-airbusds.com/files/pmedia/public/r438_9_spot_quality_performances_2013.pdf
- RD-7. Bouvet, M.; Thome, K.; Berthelot, B.; Bialek, A.; Czapla-Myers, J.; Fox, N.P.; Goryl, P.; Henry, P.; Ma, L.; Marcq, S.; Meygret, A.; Wenny, B.N.; Woolliams, E.R. RadCalNet: A Radiometric Calibration Network for Earth Observing Imagers Operating in the Visible to Shortwave Infrared Spectral Range. Remote Sens. 2019, 11, 2401, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11202401>
- RD-8. M. Cournet, A. Giros, L. Dumas, J.M. Delvit., D. Greslou, F. Languille, G. Blanchet, S. May, and J. Michel (2016). 2D Sub-Pixel Disparity Measurement Using QPEC / Medicis, Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLI-B1, 291-298, doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLI-B1-291-2016.
- RD-9. John Pike, National Image Interpretability Scale. 1998, <https://fas.org/irp/imint/niirs.htm> Accessed online: 22 October 2021
- RD-10. Zaroni, "IKONOS Signal-to-Noise Ratio Estimation", March 25-27, 2002, JACIE Workshop, 2002 <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/search.jsp?R=20040004380>
- RD-11. Sentinel-2 MPC L1C Data Quality Report, S2-PDGS-MPC-DQR, Issue 71, 03/01/2022. https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/685211/Sentinel-2_L1C_Data_Quality_Report
- RD-12. Department of the Interior U.S. Geological Survey, Landsat 8 (L8) Data Users Handbook, LSDS-1574, Version 5.0, https://prd-wret.s3-us-west-2.amazonaws.com/assets/palladium/production/atoms/files/LSDS-1574_L8_Data_Users_Handbook-v5.0.pdf

1.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

CEOS	Committee for Earth Observing Satellites
CL	Confidence Level
DGPS	Differential Global Positioning System
EDAP	Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
ESF	Edge Spread Function
FWHM	Full Width at Half Maximum
GCP	ground control points
IVOS	Infrared and Visible Optical Sensors

MS	Multispectral
MTF	Modulation Transfer Function
NIIRS	National Imagery Interpretability Rating Scale
PAN	Panchromatic
PHR	Pleiaides High-Resolution
PICS	Pseudo-invariant Calibration Sites
POI	Points of Interest
PSF	Point Spread Function
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
TOA	Top-of-Atmosphere
UDM	Unusable Data Mask
WGCV	Working Group for Calibration and Validation

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The **GRUS-1** constellation currently consists of five, optical microsatellites that provide the user community with high-resolution multispectral (**MS**) and panchromatic (**PAN**) imagery of the Earth's surface.

The preliminary data quality assessments have been performed on a small sample of **georectified, analytic GRUS-1 bundle products** that were procured from the operator, **Axelspace**, between April and December 2021. Note that any subsequent changes to the products (i.e. updated data processing) will not be fully represented here; Axelspace implements regular updates to data processing, so it is assumed the current level of product quality will continue to be maintained, at the very least, or improved upon (and the documentation updated accordingly).

The results of the aforementioned preliminary data quality assessments are summarised in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1 GRUS-1: Executive Summary

Assessment Area	Results
	GRUS-1 A - E Ground Sampling Distance / Pixel Size @ Nadir: Panchromatic: 2.5 m Multispectral: 5.0 m.
Geometric Calibration Quality	<p>Absolute Geolocation Accuracy</p> <p>The results of this assessment indicate the absolute geolocation accuracy of the multispectral and panchromatic imagery, determined using two different methods that have been applied to the same acquisitions, are of the following:</p> <p>Method 1</p> <p>12.10 m RMSE (19.6 m CE90) - Multispectral 6.76 m RMSE (10.69 m CE90) - Panchromatic</p> <p>Method 2</p> <p>6.48 m RMSE (11.95 m CE90) - Panchromatic</p> <p>The two methods have been used to ensure the preliminary results are reliable (as the methods used have different, but important, limitations relating to various satellite / sensor and data properties).</p> <p>These results indicate the minimum performance requirement, specified by the operator as 10.0 m RMSE (CE90 not provided) @ off-nadir angle < 10 °, has been met. This minimum performance requirement does not apply to the multispectral imagery, and is currently being reviewed by Axelspace.</p>
	<p>Temporal Geolocation Accuracy</p> <p>This assessment could not be performed, as a true and meaningful time series could not be constructed from the data procured (the most</p>

Assessment Area	Results
	<p>suitable site had only three acquisitions, from three different satellites, sensed only a few days apart).</p> <p>Band Co-registration Accuracy</p> <p>The results of this assessment indicate the band co-registration accuracy of the multispectral and multispectral-panchromatic band pairs is < 1 MS Pixel RMSE and < 2 MS Pixel CE90, respectively. This is of a quality that can be improved upon.</p> <p>The results also indicate consistency across all sensors (satellites), with the differences between satellites being well below sub-pixel level.</p> <p>Note: a minimum performance requirement has not been specified by the operator for this metric.</p>
<p>Radiometric Calibration Quality</p>	<p>Absolute Radiometric Accuracy</p> <p>The results of this assessment indicate the sensors are well calibrated; the absolute radiometric accuracy, for all multispectral and panchromatic bands, is < +/- 6 %.</p> <p>Note: a minimum performance requirement has not been specified by the operator for this metric.</p> <p>Temporal Radiometric Accuracy</p> <p>The results of this assessment indicate good radiometric stability across all bands. However, for a more reliable and accurate result, more products, covering a larger period of time, would need to be assessed.</p>
<p>Image Quality</p>	<p>Signal-to-Noise Ratio</p> <p>The results of this assessment indicate the average signal-to-noise ratio, for all bands, is good and stable (measured using a high reflectance site).</p> <p>Note: a minimum performance requirement has not been specified by the operator for this metric.</p> <p>Modulation Transfer Function</p> <p>The results of this assessment indicate slight degradation in image quality, specifically with regards to sharpness, as expected (visually evident as blurring). This, however, is expected as products of a lower processing level could not be procured for this assessment.</p> <p>Note: a minimum performance requirement has not been specified by the operator for this metric.</p> <p>Image Interpretability</p> <p>The results of this assessment indicate the interpretability of the imagery is good (the majority of points of interest are detectable and recognisable, barring limits on contrast and spatial resolution).</p>

Assessment Area	Results
Visual Inspections	The results of this assessment indicate the overall image quality is good, and only a small number of anomalies / artefacts were seen (e.g. processing-related errors, incorrectly flagged data in the unusable data mask, etc.).

3. EDAP QUALITY ASSESSMENT

3.1 EDAP Maturity Matrix

Table 3-1: GRUS-1 Quality Maturity Matrix

Product Information	Product Generation	Ancillary Information	Uncertainty Characterisation	Validation	Key
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Pre-Flight	Product Flags	Uncertainty Characterisation Method	Reference Data Representativeness	Not Assessed
Product Availability & Accessibility	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Post-Launch	Ancillary Data	Uncertainty Sources Included	Reference Data Quality	Not Assessable
Product Format	Additional Processing		Uncertainty Values Provided	Validation Method	Basic
User Documentation			Geolocation Uncertainty	Validation Results	Intermediate
Metrological Traceability Documentation					Good
					Excellent
					Information not public

3.1.1 Product Information

Product Details	
<i>Grade: Intermediate</i>	
<i>Justification: This section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'intermediate' because all key information is provided but not all recommended information (e.g. product version number, radiometric uncertainty, etc.).</i>	
Product Name	GRUS-1 Analytic Product
Sensor Name	GRUS-1 (A - E)
Sensor Type	Optical – Multispectral and Panchromatic Panchromatic: 450 – 900 nm Blue: 450 – 505 nm Green: 515 – 585 nm Red: 620 – 685 nm Red Edge: 705 – 745 nm Near-infrared: 770 – 900 nm
Mission Type	Satellite constellation (at current time of writing, five satellites)
Mission Orbit	Type : Sun-synchronous sub-recurrent orbit Altitude: 585 km Descending Node: 10:40 - 11:00 (local time)
Product Version Number	-
Processor Name / Version	1.0.0
Product ID	The product ID takes the following form: <SatelliteName>_<AcquisitionDatetime>_<ProductLevel>_<ImageType>_<CellID>.<Extension> All GRUS-1 products are divided into and distributed as regularly sized tiles. AxelGlobe has its own cell system whereby the Earth's surface is divided into 5x5 km square tiles with each tile having its own unique ID.
Product Processing Level	Level 3A (Georectification / Pseudo-orthorectification) The method adopted for the georectification of data is based on the application of refined geometric corrections derived from the spatial alignment with an orthorectified third-party basemap. This aim of this method, which does not require the use of a high-resolution digital elevation model, is to achieve an acceptable horizontal / planimetric geolocation accuracy.
Measured Quantity Name	16-bit scaled top-of-atmosphere reflectance (Analytic Product)
Measured Quantity Units	%
Stated Measurement Quality	Radiometric Quality: Not provided. Geometric Quality: < 10m RMSE @ Nadir
Spatial Resolution	High Resolution Multispectral @ Nadir: 5.0 m

	Panchromatic @ Nadir: 2.5 m
Spatial Coverage	Global (Swath Width @ Nadir: 55 km)
Temporal Resolution	Revisit: 3 days (latitude dependent, constellation)
Temporal Coverage	Mission Lifetime < 5 years
Point of Contact	Axelspace Corporation, Clip Nihonbashi Building 2-3F, 3-3-3 Nihonbashi-Honcho, +81-3-4405-5085
Product locator (DOI/URL)	This information is available through their online catalogue 'AxelGlobe' (https://axelglobe.com).
Conditions for access and use	The general conditions for access and use are detailed in https://www.axelglobe.com/en/terms.html , and more specific conditions for access and use are detailed in an end user license agreement that is delivered with each product.
Limitations on public access	The products are made available upon request only. These requests (orders) are placed with their sales team (online form) or through their aforementioned online catalogue.
Product Abstract	The multispectral image / analytic product "is processed with sensor and geometric correction. Pixel resolution is 2.5 m in panchromatic image and 5.0 m in multispectral image. Positional accuracy is aimed within 10-meter RMSE range. Relative/absolute radiometric correction is also applied. The pixel value for this data is obtained by scaling the reflectance at the top of the atmosphere to an unsigned 16-bit integer value" [RD-3].

Availability & Accessibility

Grade: Intermediate

Justification: This section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Intermediate' because the products and their content are compliant with some of the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) Data Principles [RD-5] for scientific data management and stewardship. The data is available to users, at cost, through an easy-to-access commercial license.

Compliant with FAIR principles	The products and their content are compliant with many of the FAIR principles. Note an End User License Agreement is supplied with each data delivery.
Data Management Plan	This is not shared by the data provider.
Availability Status	As mentioned previously, requests (orders) are placed with their sales team (online form) or through their aforementioned online catalogue.

Product Format

Grade: Good

Justification: This section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Good' because the product format and content is readable / standard and fully detailed in the relevant documentation.

Product File Format	<p>The format of the bundle products assessed here are of the following:</p> <p>Multispectral and Panchromatic Full-resolution Imagery (.GTIF)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multispectral -> layer 1: band 1 (blue), layer 2: band 2 (green), layer 3: band 3 (red), layer 4: band 4 (red edge), layer 5: band 5 (near-infrared)
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Panchromatic -> layer 1: band 0 (panchromatic) (All data is provided in the projection of the local UTM zone) <p>Multispectral and Panchromatic Product Metadata (.JSON) Multispectral and Panchromatic imagery Unusable Data Mask (UDM) (.GTIF)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invalid data layer (binary) -> no data / invalid data: 1, valid data: 0 Cloud data layer (binary) -> cloud cover: 1, cloud free: 0 <p>(Note: both sets of UDM files use the same feature detection algorithm)</p>
Metadata Conventions	The product format and content, in which standard file formats and naming conventions are used, are fully described in [RD-3].
Analysis Ready Data?	This data is not considered as analysis ready data (e.g. Committee for Earth Observing Satellites (CEOS) Analysis Ready Data, https://ceos.org/ard/).

User Documentation		
<i>Grade: Intermediate</i>		
<i>Justification: The product user guide and associated documentation, provided upon request to the data provider, contains high-level information only (e.g. satellite description, data products and description, spectral descriptions, instructions for data conversions, etc.). The documentation does contain some very high-level algorithm theoretical basis document-type information also. Therefore, the status of this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as "Intermediate".</i>		
Document	Reference	QA4ECV Compliant
Product User Guide	[RD-4]	No
ATBD	[RD-4]	No

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
<i>Grade: Not assessable.</i>	
Traceability Chain / Uncertainty Tree Diagram Available	-

3.1.2 Product Generation

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Pre-Flight	
<i>Grade: Basic</i>	
<i>Justification: There is only very high-level information relating to spatial (e.g. modulation transfer function) pre-flight sensor calibration and characterisation activities provided (i.e. none on radiometric or spectral). Therefore, as some important aspects of instrument behaviour is missing and / or is not entirely of a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose, this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Basic'.</i>	
Summary	(see above)
References	[RD-4]

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Post-Launch	
<i>Grade: Intermediate</i>	
<i>Justification: There is only high-level information relating to the geometric and radiometric post-launch sensor calibration and characterisation activities provided but as this covers the most important aspects of instrument behaviour, at a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose and uses appropriate community infrastructure/methods (CEOS/FRMs), this section of the maturity matrix has been graded</i>	

as 'Intermediate'. Note the latter cannot be assessed against the mission's stated performance, as this has not been provided (publicly).

<p>Summary</p>	<p>Radiometric</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The relative radiometric calibration activity is performed using dark (e.g. ocean at night) and flat (bright and featureless) acquisitions. The absolute radiometric calibration activity is performed by making comparisons with data (i.e. top-of-atmosphere (TOA) reflectance) from the CEOS RadCalNet sites. <p>Geometric</p> <p>The geometric calibration activity is performed using:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geometric validation is achieved with a five-stage process applying corrections for optical aberrations and band misalignment alongside registration against a basemap based on external sensors, ground control point alignment and further refinement. An automated system for testing the geometric accuracy of chosen benchmark sites is referenced using multiple ground control and automated geometric performance monitoring to identify any developing geo-accuracy problems.
<p>References</p>	<p>[RD-4]</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">Additional Processing</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Grade: Intermediate</i></p> <p><i>Justification: This section of the maturity matrix has been graded 'Intermediate' because significant additional processing steps relevant to georectification have been documented (high-level), and deemed fir for stated purpose, but not the additional processing steps relevant to the unusable data masking.</i></p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Additional Processing</p>	
<p>Summary</p>	<p>1. Georectification (Pseudo-orthorectification)</p> <p>The imagery is georectified by performing per-pixel corrections derived from the alignment of the imagery with orthorectified imagery from Sentinel-2 (validated, reliable and acceptable accuracy) that acts as a basemap (and therefore a digital elevation model is not required, as this method is capable of including corrections for topographic distortions).</p> <p>2. Unusable Data Masking</p> <p>The processing steps relevant to this mask are not detailed in the documentation provided.</p>
<p>References</p>	<p>[RD-3], [RD-4]</p>

3.1.3 Ancillary Information

Product Flags	
<i>Grade: Intermediate</i>	
<i>Justification: The products do contain per-pixel binary flags, covered by the unusable data mask, for invalid data and cloud and so this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Intermediate'.</i>	
Summary	<i>The products do contain per-pixel binary flags, covered by the unusable data mask, for invalid data and cloud.</i>
References	<i>[RD-3], [RD-4]</i>

Ancillary Data	
<i>Grade: Intermediate</i>	
<i>Justification: The product and associated documentation contain key ancillary data that is required to define the measurement data but as the uncertainties of these key ancillary data have not been quantified for these, where appropriate, this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Intermediate'.</i>	
Summary	<i>The product metadata and documentation contain a wealth of ancillary data (e.g. solar and viewing geometries, spectral responses, radiometric calibration coefficients).</i>
References	<i>[RD-3], [RD-4]</i>

3.1.4 Uncertainty Characterisation

Uncertainty Characterisation Method	
<i>Grade: Not Assessable</i>	
<i>Justification: The methods used to characterise the uncertainties associated with geometric and radiometric calibration quality are not included in the documentation made available to users, and so this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Not Assessable'.</i>	
Summary	<i>(see above)</i>
References	<i>-</i>

Uncertainty Sources Included	
<i>Grade: Not Assessable</i>	
<i>Justification: There is no information or documentation concerning the sources of uncertainty included in the pre-flight and post-launch calibration and characterisation activities. Therefore, this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Not Assessable'.</i>	
Summary	<i>(see above)</i>
References	<i>-</i>

Uncertainty Values Provided	
<i>Grade: Basic</i>	
<i>Justification: The documentation provides a single uncertainty value that is used to characterise the geometric performance of products for the mission as a whole (the latter is not provided for the radiometric performance of products), and so this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Basic'.</i>	
<i>It is recommended the operator provide uncertainty values used to characterise the radiometric performance (e.g. absolute radiometric accuracy) for the whole mission also.</i>	

Summary	(see above)
References	-

Geolocation Uncertainty	
<i>Grade: Basic</i>	
<i>Justification: A single uncertainty value is provided for the whole mission only and so this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Basic'.</i>	
Summary	<p><i>Absolute Geolocation Accuracy: 10.0 m RMSE @ off-nadir angle < 10°.</i></p> <p><i>Note: this single uncertainty value is expressed as a root mean square error, instead of a circular error associated to a certain confidence level (it is recommended that a circular error be given also as it ensures that most sources of uncertainty are taken into consideration). It is also not clear if this applies to both panchromatic and multispectral imagery (for the relevant assessments here, we assume it is only relevant to the panchromatic imagery).</i></p>
References	<i>[RD-3]</i>

3.1.5 Validation

It is important to note this section, relating to the 'Validation' column of the maturity matrix, is based on the results of the data quality assessments performed by the EDAP optical team **only** (i.e. **independently** of any data quality assessments performed by the data provider and / or operator).

Reference Data Representativeness	
<i>Grade: Basic</i>	
<i>Justification: The representativeness of used reference data (sensor data from similar or 'gold' standard missions, in-situ data, ground control data), against which this sensor data is compared against, is good but the variety of reference data is small compared with the reference data available. Therefore, this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Basic'.</i>	
Summary	(See above)
References	-

Reference Data Quality & Suitability	
<i>Grade: Intermediate</i>	
<i>Justification: The reference data quality and suitability used by EDAP comes with a single uncertainty value for the entire sensor mission, and so this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Intermediate'.</i>	
Summary	<p><i>The data used as a reference for some of the radiometric calibration quality assessments include in-situ reference data from the well-established and documented RadCalNet.</i></p> <p><i>The data used as reference for the geometric calibration quality assessments include orthorectified panchromatic imagery from SPOT-5, which is validated by CNES as 2.5 m RMSE absolute accuracy, and</i></p>

	<p>GPS-defined ground control points from field surveys (e.g. La Crau and Piedmont) with an absolute accuracy of 0.1 m.</p> <p>The data used as reference for the image quality assessments include orthorectified multispectral imagery from Pléiades.</p>
References	[RD-8], [RD-7], [RD-6]

Validation Method	
<i>Grade: Intermediate</i>	
<i>Justification: The validation methods used, despite being well-documented and used by the scientific community, produce simple uncertainty values (e.g. from a statistical distribution of results) and so this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Intermediate'.</i>	
Summary	The validation methods used to assess image quality, geometric calibration and radiometric calibration quality are all well-documented and used by the scientific community.
Reference	[RD-7], [RD-9], [RD-10]

Validation Results	
<i>Grade: Intermediate</i>	
<i>Justification: The validation results, from validation assessment performed independently of those performed by the operator, show good agreement between satellite sensor and reference measurements (and within uncertainties), with the exception for the validation results of radiometric calibration quality and so this section of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Intermediate'.</i>	
Summary	The validation results of all assessments are summarised in Section 2.
Reference	See Section 4 and 5.

4. DETAILED GRUS-1 QUALITY ASSESSMENT

4.1 Objectives

The objectives of this work are to assess all core aspects of sensor data quality (geometric calibration, radiometric calibration, image quality) against sensor and product quality requirements or specifications, using the sample of sensor products provided.

Note: for these assessments, the following terminology is used to differentiate between the two types of data being assessed:

“**Tile(s)**” – this refers to the individual GeoTIFF data files, which are aligned to a proprietary geometric mapping system called “AxelGlobe” cells consisting of 5 km x 5 km square tiles.

“**Product**” – this refers to the image mosaic resulting from the merge of all tiles supplied for a given acquisition.

4.2 Geometric Calibration Quality

4.2.1 Introduction

In this section dedicated to the geometric calibration quality, there are three assessments performed; **absolute geolocation accuracy**, **temporal geolocation accuracy** and **band co-registration accuracy**. Table 4-1 details the names of the products used in these assessments.

Table 4-1 GRUS-1 Geometric Calibration Quality Assessment Product Sample

Product	Location	Product Name	Viewing Angle (°)
LC-1	La Crau (France)	GRUS1A_20210605101335	-4.8
LC-2	La Crau (France)	GRUS1D_20210526101336	-4.2
LC-3	La Crau (France)	GRUS1E_20210531101337	-3.8
PD-1	Piedmont (Italy)	GRUS1A_20210806100505	-6.6
PD-2	Piedmont (Italy)	GRUS1E_20210719095900	0.8
PD-3	Piedmont (Italy)	GRUS1C_20210811100019	-1.6

4.2.2 Absolute Geolocation Accuracy

4.2.2.1 Description and Method I

The first method used to assess the absolute geolocation accuracy of the sensor's multispectral and panchromatic imagery was based on the use of an image matching tool, Medicis / QPEC (a zero mean normalised cross-correlation algorithm, validated sub-pixel accuracy), provided by the French space agency (CNES) [RD-8]. This tool is used to match the sensor imagery with imagery from a similar sensor that has been validated for use as reference.

The products used for this assessment are as follows:

La Crau (France)

- **Product(s): LC-1, LC-2 and LC-3 (Red Band: Pixel Size 5.0 m).**
- **Reference Product(s): <SPOT-5> (Panchromatic Band: Pixel Size 2.5 m)**

The absolute geolocation accuracy of this orthorectified reference imagery, which was delivered by CNES as free from systematic and non-systematic errors (e.g. errors due to terrain relief), has been validated as better than 2.5 m RMSE [RD-6]. The main contribution to this slightly degraded absolute accuracy was not the precision but the bias of about 1.5 m. This information is of importance when using this reference imagery.

Note: the image matching tool requires the sensor imagery be resampled to match the spatial resolution of the reference imagery and be rescaled from 16-bit to 8-bit to match the 8-bit data type / dynamic range of the reference imagery also, prior to being used as input.

Figure 4-1 Image matching is performed on the sensor imagery (top layer), from the chosen sensor products, that overlaps with the sensor imagery from the chosen reference product (middle layer). Google Satellite (bottom layer).

4.2.2.2 Results I

The results of this assessment are detailed in Table 4-2 and Table 4-3.

Note: image matching is performed at a specified confidence level (e.g. if the confidence level is set at 95 % then the image matching results will be based on pixels that have been matched with 95% confidence / certainty).

Table 4-2 Absolute Geolocation Accuracy of GRUS-1 Panchromatic Imagery: Image-matching with SPOT-5 (Confidence Level = 95%) Results.

Parameter	LC-1	LC-2	LC-3
# CL95 Matched Pixels	394/22391	339/18732	334/17173
Mean Easting Error (m)	0.14	-0.92	0.05
Mean Northing Error (m)	-0.65	-0.83	-0.81
Easting Error Standard Deviation (m)	4.67	4.80	4.16

Parameter	LC-1	LC-2	LC-3
Northing Error Standard Deviation (m)	5.10	4.82	4.84
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	4.67	4.89	4.16
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	5.14	4.89	4.91
Root Mean Square Error (m)	6.95	6.91	6.43
Circular Error @ 90% (m)	10.73	10.77	10.56

Table 4-3 Absolute Geolocation Accuracy of GRUS-1 Multispectral Imagery: Image-matching with SPOT-5 (Confidence Level = 95%) Results.

Parameter	LC-1	LC-2	LC-3
# CL95 Matched Pixels	137/6273	96/4973	41/3996
Mean Easting Error (m)	-2.39	-1.90	-1.23
Mean Northing Error (m)	-2.80	-0.86	2.21
Easting Error Standard Deviation (m)	6.81	9.47	7.94
Northing Error Standard Deviation (m)	8.33	8.47	8.72
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	7.22	9.66	8.03
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	8.79	8.51	8.99
Root Mean Square Error (m)	11.37	12.88	12.06
Circular Error @ 90% (m)	18.36	19.73	20.72

The results of this assessment indicate the average absolute geolocation accuracy of the georectified multispectral and panchromatic imagery is **12.10 RMSE (19.60 m CE90)** and **6.76 m RMSE (10.69 m CE90)**, respectively; this absolute geolocation accuracy is slightly degraded predominantly by the observed precision (standard deviation, random error contribution) in both directions. Therefore, the minimum performance requirement, which was specified as 10.0 m RMSE, has been met for the panchromatic but not for the multispectral imagery (the stated minimum performance requirement may not be applicable to the multispectral, to be addressed by the operator).

It is important to note the biggest limitation of this image matching tool, and other image matching tools, are differences in image contrast that originate from differences in viewing and solar geometries, radiometric resolution, spectral resolution, etc. The latter differences affect the number of pixels being matched and the confidence level at which they are being matched, and this is evident in the results of this assessment (i.e. the number of pixels matched is very low, even with image matching at a lower confidence level) and so they should be considered with some caution.

Note: The above limitation was proven to be the case by successfully performing imaging matching (i.e. high image matching confidence level and matched pixels) red band imagery with red band imagery from a Sentinel-2A product (e.g. S2A_MSIL1C_20210830T104021_N0301_R008_T31TFJ_20210830T124918, downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub).

This assessment was repeated, using a different method, and is covered in the following section.

Figure 4-2 For a simple visual assessment of absolute geolocation accuracy (approximation), a checkerboard of the multispectral imagery from product 2 was overlaid on top of resampled imagery from reference product. Zoomed-in, there is clear alignment between the two (i.e. good absolute geolocation accuracy). Scale 1:12000.

4.2.2.3 Description and Method II

The absolute geolocation accuracy of the sensor's georectified panchromatic imagery was assessed using a second method that directly determines the difference between the 'absolute' (actual) and apparent location of a set of ground control points (GCPs), defined by Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) during a site survey¹, in an image.

The products used for this assessment are as follows:

Product: LC-1, LC-2, LC-3, PD-1, PD-2 and PD-3.

Note: this method was used only to assess the panchromatic imagery due to the limitation imposed by the spatial resolution (i.e. this method is not suitable for the assessment of multispectral imagery due to the lower spatial resolution).

4.2.2.4 Results II

4.2.2.4.1 La Crau

The results of this assessment are detailed in Table 4-4 and Figure 4-3.

¹These field surveys were conducted by ESA for contribution to the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency's Advanced Land Observing Satellite (JAXA ALOS) optical calibration / validation activities. The accuracy of the GCPs defined by DGPS is within 0.1 m.

The results of this assessment indicate the average absolute geolocation accuracy of the sensor's georectified panchromatic imagery is **6.48m RMSE (11.95m CE90)**, which is very close to the results derived using the first method and so positively attests to the reliability of these results.

Table 4-4: La Crau: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy of GRUS-1 Panchromatic Imagery: Manual GCP Matching Results.

Parameter	LC-1	LC-2	LC-3
GCP Sample #	32	27	28
Mean Easting Error (m)	-2.2	-4.11	-2.49
Mean Northing Error (m)	-1.09	-0.27	-0.26
Easting Error Standard Deviation (m)	5.17	3.75	3.78
Northing Error Standard Deviation (m)	4.59	7.55	4.89
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	2.45	4.12	2.50
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	4.72	7.56	4.90
Root Mean Square Error (m)	5.32	8.61	5.50
Circular Error @ 90% (m)	10.38	15.50	9.96

Figure 4-3: The absolute geolocation accuracy assessment results, using the second method, plotted for product LC-1 (top left), LC-2 (top right) and LC-3 (bottom).

Figure 4-4: Examples of La Crau GCPs used in the absolute geolocation assessment taken from product LC-1. Note: if a specific GCP was not easily defined then it was removed from the assessment to reduce the impact of human error.

4.2.2.4.2 Piedmont

The results of this assessment are detailed in Table 4-5, Figure 4-5 and Figure 4-6.

The absolute geolocation accuracy of the sensor's panchromatic imagery of Piedmont (Italy) is determined by this assessment as (average) **11.83 m RMSE (20.97 m CE90)** and, therefore, does not meet the minimum performance requirement specified previously. Whilst this is to be expected, as accurate orthorectification is difficult in such areas with large topographical variations (i.e. lower accuracy, which will propagate when using orthorectified data to georectify GRUS-1 data), the biggest contribution to this degraded accuracy is due to the degraded accuracy of ground control points used. The latter is due to the challenges inherent in surveying mountainous topographies.

Table 4-5: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy results for Piedmont

Parameter	PD-1	PD-2	PD-3
Off-nadir Angle (°)	-6.60	0.80	-1.60
GCP Sample #	28	21	26
Mean Easting Error (m)	-1.21	-9.50	-7.44
Mean Northing Error (m)	-6.37	-1.87	-2.45
Easting Error Standard Deviation (m)	16.68	7.19	5.11
Northing Error Standard Deviation (m)	7.29	7.25	8.18
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	6.48	9.68	7.83
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	9.68	7.49	8.54
Root Mean Square Error (m)	11.65	12.24	11.59
Circular Error @ 90% (m)	25.90	19.36	17.36

Figure 4-5: A screen capture of a small sample of GCPs used in the absolute geolocation accuracy assessment of Piedmont data. Blue labels indicate 'actual' location of GPS-defined GCPs and the Red labels indicate 'apparent' location - the displacement between them is a measure of the absolute geolocation accuracy.

Figure 4-6: The absolute geolocation accuracy assessment results, using the second method, plotted for product PD1-1 (top left), PD-2 (top right) and PD-3 (bottom left).

4.2.3 Temporal Geolocation Accuracy

This assessment could not be performed, as a true and meaningful time series could not be constructed from the data procured (the most suitable site had only three acquisitions, from three different satellites, sensed only a few days apart).

4.2.4 Band Co-registration Accuracy

4.2.4.1 Description and Method

The band co-registration accuracies have been determined for adjacent multispectral and multispectral-panchromatic band pairs, using the aforementioned image-matching tool (described in Section 4.2.2.1). The products used for this assessment are the following:

Product(s): LC-1 (1 tile), LC-2 (150 tiles), LC-3 (148 tiles), LC-1 (196 tiles)

Note: the panchromatic imagery is downsampled to match the spatial resolution of the multispectral imagery when performing the co-registration assessment of multispectral-panchromatic band pairs.

4.2.4.2 Results

The results of this assessment are detailed in Table 4-6 and Table 4-7.

Table 4-6: Band Co-registration Accuracy Assessment Results of Product GRUS-1A (1 tile) – Confidence Level = 99%, Units: MS Pixel

GRUS-1 A (LC-1)	MS				MS-PAN
	Band 1 & 2	Band 2 & 3	Band 3 & 4	Band 4 & 5	Band 5 & PAN
# CL95 Matched Pixels	212 / 355	227 / 374	35 / 205	97 / 318	42 / 201
Mean Easting Error (m)	-0.48	-0.05	0.53	-0.23	0.02
Mean Northing Error	0.16	0.03	0.23	-0.56	0.56
Easting Error Standard Deviation	0.49	0.64	0.44	0.62	0.51
Northing Error Standard Deviation	0.41	0.46	0.46	0.80	0.90
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	0.02	0.90	0.51	1.06	0.51
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	0.44	0.46	0.51	0.98	1.06
RMSE	0.82	0.79	0.86	1.18	1.17
CE90	1.15	1.18	1.34	1.63	1.58

Table 4-7: Band Co-registration Accuracy Assessment Results of Product products GRUS-1D, GRUS-1E, and GRUS-1A (all tiles) – Confidence Level = 99 %, Units: MS Pixel

GRUS-1 D (LC-2)	MS				MS-PAN
Band Pairs	Band 1 & 2	Band 2 & 3	Band 3 & 4	Band 4 & 5	Band 5 & PAN
# CL95 Matched Pixels	19773/37712	23362/41891	4320/22638	10993/36312	6072/27901
Mean Easting Error (m)	0.05	0.05	-0.06	-0.02	-0.27
Mean Northing Error	-0.00	0.01	-0.03	-0.06	0.11
Easting Error Standard Deviation	0.43	0.48	0.62	0.56	0.81
Northing Error Standard Deviation	0.63	0.65	0.84	0.76	0.97
Easting Root Mean Square Error	0.44	0.48	0.63	0.56	0.85
Northing Root Mean Square Error	0.63	0.65	0.84	0.76	0.97
RMSE	0.76	0.81	1.05	0.95	1.29
CE90	1.19	1.25	1.62	1.47	1.09
GRUS-1E (LC-3)	MS				MS-PAN
Band Pairs	Band 1 & 2	Band 2 & 3	Band 3 & 4	Band 4 & 5	Band 5 & PAN
# CL95 Matched Pixels	16324/35028	21008 / 40319	4193 / 2162	9974 / 35132	5880 / 27388
Mean Easting Error (m)	-0.04	0.04	-0.07	-0.04	-0.19
Mean Northing Error	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.03	-0.07
Easting Error Standard Deviation	0.58	0.56	0.70	0.68	0.80
Northing Error Standard Deviation	0.67	0.64	0.82	0.77	1.12
Easting Root Mean Square Error	0.58	0.56	0.70	0.68	0.83
Northing Root Mean Square Error	0.67	0.64	0.82	0.77	1.12
RMSE	0.88	0.85	1.08	1.03	1.39
CE90	1.35	1.30	1.66	1.58	0.99
GRUS-1A (LC-1)	MS				MS-PAN
Band Pairs	Band 1 & 2	Band 2 & 3	Band 3 & 4	Band 4 & 5	Band 5 & PAN
# CL95 Matched Pixels	21179 / 52178	25522/60556	6071/39984	12969/52965	6816/40809

Mean Easting Error (m)	0.02	-0.05	0.00	0.05	0.10
Mean Northing Error	0.07	-0.03	0.00	-0.06	0.18
Easting Error Standard Deviation	0.65	0.64	0.73	0.75	0.84
Northing Error Standard Deviation	0.63	0.66	0.76	0.83	0.84
Easting Root Mean Square Error	0.65	0.64	0.73	0.75	0.84
Northing Root Mean Square Error	0.63	0.66	0.76	0.83	0.85
RMSE	0.91	0.93	1.06	1.12	1.21
CE90	1.372	1.41	1.65	1.70	0.94

These results indicate the band co-registration for the multispectral and multispectral-panchromatic band pairs is reasonable, but there is room for improvement especially when compared to the band co-registration accuracy of data from a “gold standard” mission such as Sentinel-2 (minimum performance requirement is 0.3 MS Pixel CE99.7 [RD-11], and similar for data from some HR sensors). The results also indicate the band co-registration for the multispectral and multispectral-panchromatic band pairs and is consistent between sensors. Note: a minimum performance requirement has not been specified by the operator for this metric.

In addition to the above, the error budget is computed and it is based on the rule that pixel displacement errors are transitive across all band pairs - by summing the displacement for all band pairs (e.g. (1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 4), (4,5),(5,PAN)), the result is in the same order of displacement for the band pair (1, 5), as shown in the equation below:

$$D_{1,PAN} \cong D_{1,2} + D_{2,3} + D_{3,4} + D_{4,5} + D_{5,PAN}$$

Where $D_{1,PAN}$ stands for displacement between band 1 and 5 (calculated for the easting and northing direction). The displacement error across all bands is (average) is 0.03 and 0.014 in the easting and northing directions, respectively.

4.3 Radiometric Calibration Quality

4.3.1 Introduction

In this section dedicated to the radiometric calibration quality, there are two assessments performed - **absolute radiometric accuracy** and **temporal radiometric accuracy**. Table 4-8 details the names of the products used in these assessments.

Table 4-8 GRUS-1 Radiometric Calibration Quality Assessment Product Sample

Product ID ²	Product or Tile Name	Viewing Angle (°)
1 (B)	GRUS1C_20210714031349_L3A (MSI/PAN_N40181857.tif)	1.8
2 (LC)	GRUS1A_20210605101335_L3A (MSI/PAN_N43120078.tif)	-4.8
3 (G1)	GRUS1A_20201118102137_L3A (MSI/PAN_S23130310.tif)	-2.51

² (B) – Baotou (China), (LC) – La Crau (France), (G) – Gobabeb (Namibia), (L) – PICS Libya-4 (Libya).

4 (G2)	GRUS1A_20200621102445_L3A (MSI/PAN_S23130310.tif)	2.91
5 (G3)	GRUS1A_20200527102447_L3A (MSI/PAN_S23130310.tif)	4.81
6 (L1)	GRUS1A_20210301091454_L3A	-2.92
7 (L2)	GRUS1A_20210204091704_L3A	-5.69
8 (L3)	GRUS1A_20201228091607_L3A	-0.20

4.3.2 Absolute Radiometric Accuracy

4.3.2.1 Description and Method

The radiometric calibration, or correction, of sensor data sees to the successful conversion of raw data (i.e. digital numbers) to spectral radiance or reflectance, using the relevant coefficients (e.g. physical bias, physical gain, solar spectral irradiance constants). This is important as it improves the interpretability and quality of the sensor data (and is particularly important when comparing multiple sensor datasets over a period of time, which is commonly performed by the scientific community).

The method used to determine the absolute radiometric calibration accuracy of the sensor's bands is based on comparing the TOA reflectance values derived from the sensors acquisitions of the chosen RadCalNet calibration sites with the TOA reflectance values derived from the RadCalNet calibration sites themselves (i.e. simulated TOA reflectance values).

The RadCalNet calibration sites, operated by the CEOS Working Group for Calibration and Validation (**WGCV**) Infrared and Visible Optical Sensors (**IVOS**), provides the scientific community with the following:

- TOA reflectance values, derived from both in-situ surface and atmosphere measurements (e.g. surface pressure, columnar water vapour, columnar ozone, aerosol optical depth, etc.) that are **SI-traceable**, at:
 - 30-minute intervals between 09:00 and 15:00 local standard time (cloud-free data only), and 10 nm spectral sample intervals between 400 nm and 1000 nm.

Note: the RadCalNet TOA reflectance values are representative of nadir viewing observations only, so comparison to sensor TOA reflectance values should be used with caution - when the sensor viewing zenith angle deviates significantly from nadir, both atmospheric and surface non-Lambertian behaviour can lead to significant deviation from at-nadir simulated signal. The correction for the latter (i.e. off-nadir viewing angle effects), as well as illumination (solar) angle effects, can be done using bi-directional reflectance modelling.

The products used to assess the absolute radiometric calibration accuracy, by temporal and spectral simulation with RadCalNet data, are the following:

Product(s): Product 1 (B), 2 (LC), 3 (G1), 4 (G2), 5 (G3)

These products provide acquisitions of the chosen RadCalNet sites at Baotou (see Table 4-9), Gobabeb (see Table 4-10) and La Crau (see Table 4-11).

Table 4-9: La Crau RadCalNet Site Description

Parameter	Description
Geographic Location	Latitude: 43.558889, Longitude: 4.864167, Altitude: 20 m
Characteristics	The RadCalNet top-of-atmosphere reflectance spectra are representative of a disk of 30 m radius.

Table 4-10: Gobabeb RadCalNet Calibration Site Description

Parameter	Description
Geographic Location	Latitude: -23.6002, Longitude: 15.1196, Altitude: 510 m
Characteristics	The RadCalNet top-of-atmosphere reflectance spectra are representative of a disk of 30 m radius.

Table 4-11: Baotou RadCalNet Calibration Site Description

Parameter	Description
Geographic Location	Latitude: 40.8514, Longitude 109.6291, Altitude 1307m
Characteristics	The RadCalNet top-of-atmosphere reflectance spectra are representative of a grey gravel square (so-called instrument 2 data). Each square is about 48m across.

These analytical products contain data stored as scaled TOA reflectance and therefore the user only needs to apply the scaling factor as per the following:

$$L = DN(b) * 0.001$$

Equation 1 This basic formula is used for digital number (DN) to unscaled TOA reflectance (L) conversion of sensor data, per band (b). Note: the use of DN here refers to scaled TOA reflectance values rather than what it commonly refers to, which is uncalibrated intensity values.

The determined absolute radiometric calibration accuracy cannot be evaluated against a minimum performance requirement as it has not been specified by the operator. Instead, this will be evaluated against what is generally considered very good, based on similar sensors such as Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 (OLI), which is approximately < 5 % for all bands [RD-11, RD-12].

4.3.2.2 Results

The results of this assessment are detailed in Table 4-12.

The results are expressed as a difference, which is expressed as a percentage, between GRUS-1 TOA reflectances ($\rho_{b \text{ work}}$) and simulated GRUS-1 TOA reflectances ($\rho_{b \text{ simulated}}$) and is calculated as follows:

$$\rho_b = ((\rho_b \text{ simulated} - \rho_b \text{ work}) / (\rho_b \text{ simulated})) * 100$$

Equation 2 – Absolute Radiometric Accuracy % Difference

Table 4-12: Radiometric calibration results for GRUS-1 products over the RadCalNet sites located at La Crau, Gobabeb and Baotou.

Product	Origin	Blue	Green	Red	Red Edge	NIR	PAN
1	Sensor	0.1682	0.1711	0.1804	0.1668	0.1807	0.1732
	RadCalNet	0.1649	0.1694	0.1827	0.1769	0.2084	0.1842
	ρ_b	2.00	1.01	-1.30	-6.03	-15.32³	-6.35
2	Sensor	0.1326	0.1297	0.1296	0.1752	0.2306	0.1535
	RadCalNet	0.1229	0.1211	0.1350	0.1838	0.2391	0.1528
	ρ_b	7.87	7.15	-3.97	-4.71	-3.56	0.45
3	Sensor	0.2085	0.2354	0.3179	0.3471	0.3579	0.2956
	RadCalNet	0.1959	0.2251	0.3045	0.3128	0.3394	0.2717
	ρ_b	-6.42	-4.56	-4.40	-10.98	-5.46	-8.78
4	Sensor	0.2077	0.2303	0.3099	0.3341	0.3469	0.2772
	RadCalNet	0.1982	0.2278	0.3073	0.3316	0.3494	0.2884
	ρ_b	-4.73	-1.07	-0.85	-0.73	0.71	-4.04
5	Sensor	0.2058	0.2454	0.3324	0.3376	0.3669	0.2945
	RadCalNet	0.2116	0.2433	0.3345	0.3609	0.3797	0.3042
	ρ_b	-2.83	0.85	-0.63	-6.89	-3.49	-3.28

Table 4-13: GRUS-1 Sensor Observation Conditions (Solar and Viewing Geometries)

Product	Sensor Viewing Angle (°)	Sensor Azimuth Angle (°)	Solar Elevation Angle (°)	Solar Azimuth Angle (°)	Water Vapour (g/cm)	AOD ()
1 (B)	1.80	77.29	62.65	127.73	2.23	0.23
2 (LC)	-4.80	257.55	62.68	133.54	0.97	0.08
3 (G1)	-2.51	257.33	83.37	52.36	1.06	0.05
4 (G2)	2.91	77.10	42.20	11.08	0.41	0.03

³ This measurement was assessed twice, along with visual inspections of the sensor and reference RadCalNet data, and no apparent anomalies were observed.

5 (G3)	4.81	77.13	44.45	10.16	1.23	0.02
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The results of this assessment indicate the data is very well calibrated – the average absolute radiometric accuracy is approximately $\pm 5\%$ for all bands. This is to be expected as the radiometric quality of the data is regularly monitored by the operator (regular observations of RadCalNet calibration sites around the world are made in order to perform regular relative / absolute radiometric calibration [RD-4]). Note: additional corrections (e.g. corrections for bi-directional reflectance) were not deemed necessary here as the viewing geometries, detailed in Table 4-13 along with the solar geometries, were within ideal limits (e.g. viewing angle $< 5^\circ$).

4.3.3 Temporal Radiometric Accuracy

4.3.3.1 Description and Method

The temporal radiometric accuracy is determined by performing linear regression on a time-series of mean TOA reflectance (calculated for a defined area of interest, since launch). The products used for this assessment are of the following:

Product(s): 6 (L1), 7 (L2), 8 (L3) (GRUS-1A only)

Figure 4-7 Mosaic of nine ties from each product covering 15 x 5 Shapefile representing defined area of interest

The defined area of interest, as shown in Figure 4-7, is included in the CEOS Pseudo-invariant Calibration Sites (**PICS**) Libya-4 site that is well known for its **high radiometric stability**.

Note: a minimum performance requirement has not been specified by the operator.

4.3.3.2 Results

The results of this assessment are shown in Table 4-14 and Figure 4-8; the temporal radiometric accuracy, which is determined by a linear regression model, indicates general radiometric stability across all bands. However, for a more reliable and accurate result, more products, covering a longer period of time, would need to be assessed.

Table 4-14: Temporal Radiometric Accuracy Results

Band	Temporal Radiometric Accuracy (% / day)
Blue	0.0031
Green	0.0059

Red	0.0063
Red Edge	0.0033
Near Infrared	0.0087
Panchromatic	0.0009

Note: this assessment was performed using only three products from one satellite and so this result cannot be applied to the remaining five satellites in the constellation.

Figure 4-8: The temporal radiometric accuracy of GRUS-1 A (TOA reflectance vs. number of days since launch).

4.4 Image Quality

4.4.1 Introduction

This section describes the assessment of product image quality on the supplied sensor products in terms of **Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)**, **Modulation Transfer Function (MTF)**, **Image Interpretability** and general **Visual Inspections**.

Table 4-15 GRUS-1 Image Quality Assessment Product Sample

Product	Location	Product Name	Viewing Angle (°)
6 (L1)	PICS Libya-4 (Libya)	GRUS1A_20210301091454_L3A (*PAN/MSI*_N28070458.tif)	-2.92
7 (L2)	PICS Libya-4 (Libya)	GRUS1A_20210204091704_L3A(*PAN/MSI*_N28060459.tif)	-5.69
9 (L4)	PICS Libya-4 (Libya)	GRUS1A_20210216091215_L3A (*PAN/MSI*_N28090464.tif)	4.49
10 (B1)	Baotou (China)	GRUS1C_20210511031459_L3A (PAN_N40181857.tif)	0.7

4.4.2 Signal-to-Noise Ratio

4.4.2.1 Description and Method

The SNR is used to quantify the performance of a sensor in response to a particular exposure; it quantifies the ratio of the sensor's output signal to the noise present in the output signal and can be expressed by the following:

$$SNR = \frac{\mu}{\sigma}$$

Where μ is the mean signal and σ is the standard deviation of the signal.

The method proposed for this assessment allows for the estimation of (spatial) SNR, based on the aforementioned equation and the following assumption:

- The mean signal is defined as the spatial average of a group of pixels observing a spatially varying scene and the noise is defined as the standard deviation of this signal for the same group of pixels.

The method, described in [RD-10], is performed for each spectral band, whose imagery has been converted from DN to TOA radiance (as seen in Equation 1), in the following way:

1. Compute the local statistics of a small (5 x 5 pixels) sliding window applied to the imagery being assessed. Select only the "best" small windows for the following steps.
 - a. The selection of small windows ensures that increased site uniformity is generally maintained (if not, where spatially high frequencies exist (e.g. sharp transitions seen as dune summits - dedicated image processing is applied in order to detect this and filter (e.g. Sobel Filter)).
2. Compute the statistical distribution (histogram), between the **minimum** and **maximum radiance**, of the selected "best" small windows (statistics of 5 x 5 pixel windows) – the signal is defined as the peak (i.e. mean radiance) of this statistical distribution and the noise is defined as the standard deviation of this statistical distribution about the mean.
3. Estimate SNR(s).

The products used for this assessment are of the following:

Product(s): Product 6 (L), 7 (L), 9 (L)

Figure 4-9: An example of PAN data utilised for the SNR assessment over PICS Libya-4. This site is used for the important spectral, spatial and temporal properties that PICS are characterised by.

4.4.2.2 Results

The results of this assessment are detailed in Table 4-16.

Table 4-16 SNR Assessment Results

Band	Mean Radiance $W.m^{-2}.sr^{-1}$	SNR	Mean Radiance $W.m^{-2}.sr^{-1}$	SNR	Mean Radiance $W.m^{-2}.sr^{-1}$	SNR
/	Product 6		Product 7		Product 9	
Blue	127.29	108.75	87.9	95.0	121.34	91.46
Green	147.05	133.06	111.66	121.88	137.11	103.85
Red	175.38	133.15	154.55	113.57	171.12	105.79
Red Edge	160.20	109.88	164.15	94.23	156.40	93.96
NIR	215.42	137.18	186.5	122.56	207.41	116.4
PAN	160.41	198.84	123.57	164.77	152.93	160.53

Figure 4-10: The SNR results for Product 6 PAN band.

The results generally indicate above satisfactory and stable SNR values for all multispectral and panchromatic bands.

There is no minimum performance requirement specified by the operator publicly, but the operator agreed to share the latter, along with their methodology, with us in order to allow the comparison of results. However, a direct comparison could not be made as an entirely different method was used as well as different types of input acquisitions (radiometrically “bright” acquisitions were not used).

4.4.3 Modulation Transfer Function

4.4.3.1 Description and Method

The MTF importantly describes the response of the imaging sensor as a function of spatial frequency, and so is strongly related to concepts such as sharpness, contrast and spatial resolution. Therefore, it is considered as an important image quality metric.

(It is important that this image quality metric be monitored post-launch or in orbit, not just pre-launch, in order to ensure that launch vibrations, transitions from air to vacuum, or changes in thermal state, have not degraded the sharpness of the optical imagery.)

The products used for this assessment include:

Product(s): Product 10 (B1) Panchromatic only

Note: products of a lower processing level could not be procured for this particular assessment (higher processing levels commonly include resampling kernels that introduce a smoothing effect and therefore degrades the true MTF).

This assessment has been performed using an open-source tool, validated against third party software, made publicly available at https://github.com/JorgeGIIIG/MTF_Estimator. The tool, accompanied by detailed documentation that includes information on the algorithm (Slanted-Edge based) used, works in the following way:

1. Select a band and create a Shapefile that defines the target edge to be used:
 - a. The target edge must be straight and sharp (a man-made target is more likely to have these features) and defined by uniform high and low reflectance surfaces.
 - b. The target edge must be vertical (i.e. the angle is important). This is an important requirement related to how the algorithm works - if an along-track or across-track assessment is needed then the image can be rotated accordingly.

2. Run the tool
 - a. The data in each transect (each image row), defined by the Shapefile, is smoothed and then differentiated in order to obtain a coarse estimation of the pixel position of the target edge. The latter estimation is then used to set the initial conditions of the optimisation technique that is used to fit a sigmoid function to the data (as shown in Figure 4-11).

Figure 4-11 The sigmoid function (-) is fitted to the data (●) in a transect. The point of inflexion (x) shows the estimated sub-pixel edge position. X axis is pixels, y axis is digital numbers

- b. The estimated sub-pixel position data for all transects is subjected to linear regression in order to ensure the target edge is straight as assumed (any outliers are removed during this process) and the target edge angle estimated.
- c. The estimated sub-pixel edge position is used to shift each transect to a common origin, hence creating a supersampled virtual edge which is modelled as a spline and thus a representation of the Edge Spread Function (**ESF**).

d. The (two-dimensional) Point Spread Function (**PSF**) is obtained by fitting the spline shape to a Gaussian function using Levenberg-Marquardt optimisation.

i. The PSF defines the apparent shape of a point target as it appears in the resulting image. Therefore, it is directly related to the sharpness of images provided by the sensor / imaging system.

e. The MTF is then estimated from the modulus of the Fourier transform of the PSF.

i. The MTF informs on the contrast of the different spatial frequency components of the observed image.

The operator has specified in [RD-4], that the spatial clarity of the imagery is assessed both pre-launch, using lab-acquired imagery, and post-launch on a regular basis (this ensures the focal lengths for each sensor are optimised. The assessment is also performed post-processing in order to understand if any effects of processing are reducing image clarity.

Note: no minimum requirement has been specified by the operator for this image quality metric.

Figure 4-12: Baotou Artificial MTF Target: GRUS-1 (Left) and Google Satellite (Image 2022 © Maxar Technologies) (Right).

4.4.3.2 Results

The results of this assessment are shown in Figure 4-13.

Figure 4-13: MTF results for Baotou MTF target (Along-track Profile). The (top left) transects successfully used to detect the sub-pixel location of the edge (i.e. supersampled edge), (top right) supersampled edge (light blue), the best-fit Gaussian resulting from the optimisation used (brown), optimised ESF spline numeric model (red) and optimised PSF spline numeric model (blue). The (bottom left) MTF modulus estimation.

The results of this assessment indicate the following:

- The estimated effective resolution of the image, which can be translated as the Full Width at Half Maximum (**FWHM**) of the PSF, is three times greater than the intended effective resolution of the image. Note: the latter is also used by the operator to determine the effective resolution of GRUS-1 products.
- The $MTF@N_f$ is 0.02.
 - The sampling period or frequency is usually defined by the ground sampling distance or by the corresponding Nyquist frequency (N_f) which is defined as half the inverse of the ground sampling distance (for example, for GRUS-1 Pan $N_f = 0.2$). Given a ground sampling distance, the N_f essentially corresponds to the highest spatial frequency that can be represented by the imaging system (i.e. signals with spatial frequencies higher than N_f cannot be reliably reproduced and can cause aliasing).

Note: the MTF could not be assessed in the across-track direction as the across-track edge, between the black and white boxes of the MTF target, could not be detected by the tool.

Note: the condition of imaging data needs to be taken into consideration: cloud, noise, product processing level, along or across direction of flight, viewing and illumination geometries, storage format, and size of target / spatial resolution relationship.

4.4.4 Image Interpretability

4.4.4.1 Description and Method

The image interpretability of optical sensor imagery is an important aspect of image quality (originating from the actual sensor or image processing), especially in terms of their practical use or application. This is commonly assessed, subjectively, using a well-defined procedure that is based on the successful interpretation of objects or features according to the National Imagery Interpretability Rating Scale⁴ (**NIIRS**) category in which the sensor belongs. This well-defined procedure also importantly allows for the cross-comparison of image quality from similar sensors.

The products used for this assessment are the following:

Salon-de-Provence (France)

Mosaicked product – consisting of 59 products

Reference Product: < Pleiades >

The method used to assess image interpretability consists of clipping 100 x 100 pixel windows from the sensor's imagery (for each band), centred on the points of interest (objects or features). Note: the reference imagery is processed in order to ensure the pixel size of the reference imagery matches that of this sensor's imagery.

The point(s) of interest (**POI**) used for this assessment are defined in Table 4-17. The latter are deemed suitable for **NIIRS Category 2 (4.5 – 9.0m)** imagery for the multispectral and **NIIRS category 3 (2.5 – 4.5)** for the panchromatic imagery.

Note: comparisons are made with clips from a 'gold standard' reference mission (e.g. Pléiades High-Resolution (**PHR**) imagery (bands 1 – 3 only)), following downsampling of the spatial resolution to match the spatial resolution of GRUS-1, also.

Table 4-17: Image Interpretability POI in Salon-de-Provence

wkgt_geom (UTM 31)	Id	Description
Point (671090.3105554151115939 4830278.58671295549720526)	1	Modulation Transfer Function target
Point (671364.24309313111007214 4833044.0252351425588131)	2	Motorway / sharp transition (45° NE)
Point (668580.81736886233557016 4828965.45189037173986435)	3	Forest

⁴ <https://fas.org/irp/imint/niirs.htm>

wkgt_geom (UTM 31)	Id	Description
Point (670056.62237295764498413 4828905.08180973120033741)	4	Roundabout / parking lot
Point (669985.90922565956134349 4832120.72269264236092567)	5	Elevated tree
Point (669956.03863696497865021 4832655.53592716064304113)	6	Motorway / roundabout
Point (670564.24590074480511248 4833363.40447467099875212)	7	Dam
Point (669836.88448120269458741 4832528.00618595350533724)	8	Big building (shadow)
Point (670518.95015854423400015 4829513.56928175128996372)	9	Landing track - 34
Point (670249.72702971810940653 4831735.0312919020652771)	10	Floor painting
Point (670900.38168655894696712 4829617.21182315889745951)	11	Crop fields / sparse
Point (671548.0352310094749555 4830292.1131860688328743)	12	Broad-leaved woodland
Point (671099.93821095407474786 4828090.14610077627003193)	13	Crop fields
Point (671156.44116920174565166 4828825.77096180152148008)	14	Bridge and water
Point (671120.4438803291413933 4827691.31545618735253811)	15	Crop fields
Point (670328.31568091106601059 4831489.30539688002318144)	16	Building / EA 15
Point (671516.86161747551523149 4833207.41657157335430384)	17	Greenhouse
Point (669996.87127304612658918 4829099.09009433817118406)	18	Parking lot
Point (670062.87681329366751015 4829781.35287734866142273)	19	Plane parking
Point (670860.46870227111503482 4831527.10888031311333179)	20	Plane hangar
Point (671802.47347140731289983 4832385.40385554917156696)	21	Small crop fields
Point (671246.59432400949299335 4832300.03732818737626076)	22	Urban city

4.4.4.2 Results

GRUS-1 / Pléiades MS Band 1

GRUS-1 / Pléiades MS Band 2

GRUS-1 / Pléiades MS Band 3

GRUS-1 MS Band 4

GRUS-1 MS Band 5

GRUS-1 PAN

The result of this assessment indicates the interpretability of the imagery, across all bands, is reasonable but, through comparisons with reference imagery, there is some room for improvement (e.g. reduction of blurring).

4.4.5 Visual Inspections

4.4.5.1 Description and Method

General visual inspections were performed on the multispectral and panchromatic imagery included in the sample of products procured (one product for each site selected), in order to ensure there were no anomalies or artefacts present. The results are detailed in below.

4.4.5.2 Results

The results are detailed in Table 4-18.

Table 4-18 GRUS-1 Visual Inspection Results

Product	Visual Inspection Comment	
<p>Name 1D_20210605</p> <p>Location La Crau</p> <p>No. Tiles 196/196</p>	<p>Multispectral: The multispectral image appears to contain an anomaly / artefact (band 1 and 2 only), which takes the form of a horizontal and vertical line across the image. This anomaly / artefact is correctly flagged as 'invalid data' in the 'no data' layer of the UDM but incorrectly flagged as 'cloud area' in the 'cloud cover' layer of the UDM.</p> <p>Panchromatic: This panchromatic image appears to contain an anomaly /</p>	

	<p>artefact but this has not been flagged in the 'no data' layer of the UDM.</p>	<p>1 MS: This horizontal anomaly / artefact is evident in the multispectral bands (above, left) but is not flagged in the 'no data' layer of the UDM (right).</p> <p>1 PAN: This anomaly / artefact is present in panchromatic imagery (above, left) but it is not flagged by the 'no data' layer of the UDM.</p>
<p>Name 1A_20210216 Location Libya No. Tiles 87 / 87</p>	<p>Multispectral: This multispectral image appears to contain an anomaly / artefact in band 3 and band 5. These take the form of dark spots, which do not appear to be cloud shadow, and are partially flagged as 'cloud area' in the 'cloud cover' layer of the UDM for band 3 but not at all for band 5.</p> <p>Panchromatic: This panchromatic image appears to contain the aforementioned anomaly / artefact but it is not being flagged in either layer of the UDM. Also, cloud is only partially flagged in the 'cloud cover' layer of the UDM.</p>	<p>Here is an example of the full panchromatic mosaic with the associated 'cloud cover' layer of the</p>

		UDM mosaic - cloud is present but not flagged.
Name 1A_20210513 Location Gobabeb No. Tiles 1 / 1	Multispectral: No anomalies / artefacts observed. Panchromatic: No anomalies / artefacts observed.	

There is a minor observation on the accuracy of cloud detection also – the areas of high reflectance (e.g. metal roofing) are incorrectly flagged as ‘cloud area’ in the ‘cloud cover’ layer of the UDM (right). This is a common issue with cloud detection algorithms.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This technical note details the preliminary data quality assessments (including geometric calibration, radiometric calibration and image quality) performed on a very small sample of **georectified GRUS-1 bundle products**. The results of the aforementioned data quality assessments generally indicate the quality of the data (products) produced is **good**. However, it is recommended that the data provider / operator address, at the very least, the following:

- The format of the product metadata; the metadata currently contained within the JSON format, which contains per tile information and general data variables, could be improved by converting the JSON into a GeoJSON or Shapefile format to allow for easier mapping / usage of the tiles contained within 3rd party software (QGIS, etc.). Mapping is already present in Axelspace data portal but 3rd party software compatibility will be of great benefit for advanced users.
- The provision of all minimum performance requirements so that it is clear to users what level of data quality, especially geometrically and radiometrically, can be guaranteed or expected.

APPENDIX A GRUS-1 TEST DATASET

Product ID	Location	Tiles
1A_20210605101335	La Crau	196
1D_20210526101336	La Crau	150
1E_20210531101337	La Crau	148
1A_20210806100505	Piedmont	155
1E_20210719095900	Piedmont	123
1C_20210811100019	Piedmont	132
1A_20210301091454	Libya	9
1A_20210204091704	Libya	9
1A_20201228091607	Libya	9
1A_20210513101354	Gobabeb	1
1A_20200527102447	Gobabeb	1
1A_20201118102137	Gobabeb	1
1A_20200621102445	Gobabeb	1

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